

AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

DEVELOPMENTS OF STATE POLICY OF GEORGIA ON ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT IN AGRICULTURE

Pavliashvili S.,

Doctor of Economics, Professor, Academician,

Tokmazishvili M.

Doctor of Economics, Professor, Eastern European University

Abstract

The article describes agro-technological difficulties and environmental changes in Georgian agriculture that have an economic and social impact on agrarian relations. Additionally, the potential possibilities of agricultural development to neutralize negative changes in the environment are presented. It is noted that to develop the agricultural sector and mitigate the effects of climate change and reduce emissions, activities should be conducted in three directions: technological, economic-institutional, and social. A description of each of them is provided, and the emphasis is made on agro-technological innovations, rational management, and security measures, as well as on green financing opportunities and defining social progress.

Keywords: Georgia, Agriculture, climate, technological, economic-institutional, social strategy.

Georgia has a geographical location characterized by multiple reliefs, diverse land, and a specific climate that covers almost all climatic zones, and causes many negative consequences of environmental change. Environmental attributes affect the productivity of agricultural labor and its yield, as well as cause changes in climatic conditions.¹

According to the Strategy of Agriculture and Rural Development of Georgia (2021-2027), the characteristics of Georgia are processes such as the increase of the dry area of regions; the activation of soil salinization processes; rapid mineralization and degradation of soil organic matter; increase in intensity and frequency of frosts associated with lowering humidity; the creation of favorable conditions for the spread of pests and diseases due to the increase in temperature in winter; the activation of erosion processes in some humid regions due to the growth of sediments (Agriculture and Rural Development Strategy of Georgia 2021 – 2027).

In Eastern Georgia, most crops are sensitive to climate change, such as wheat, sunflower, vegetables, and corn; in South Georgia - potatoes. The crops in Western Georgia - tea, citrus, vines, and corn - are less sensitive to climate change. Despite such a difference in the climatic conditions of both sides of the country, requirements for agricultural development contain adaptation to environmental conditions and neutralization and mitigation of the negative consequences of interaction with it. It is an actual topic, the interest of which is growing more and more.

Climate change causes soil erosion, destruction of windbreaks, washing away, and acidification. Drought has increased in the bar, and rainfall in the mountains, the growing season has changed, the vegetation period has shortened, the adaptability of crops has changed according to zones, pests and diseases have multiplied,

their reproduction periods have been extended, new kinds of viruses and rodents have appeared.

Agriculture's impact on climate change is exacerbated by the use of synthetic fertilizers, ether fermentation of domestic animals, manure management, etc.

Agriculture accounts for 25.5% of greenhouse gas emissions in Georgia, and carbon dioxide and methane emissions related to animal husbandry account for 14.5% of human-caused emissions, that is more than in the transportation sector. As a whole, 30% of harmful emission caused by human activity is created in agriculture. 35% of agricultural land is degraded (Shatberashvili E, 2014).

In addition to agro-technological difficulties, environmental changes also have social impacts related to food security and safety, the continued physical and economic access of all people to sufficient, safe, and varied food necessary for their active and healthy lives, as well as price increases further exacerbate poverty in rural and urban areas and affects the public health status of the country; the cultural and traditional attitude of the population to the land and its management gives rise to such social processes as two-way migration from the city to the countryside in the summer and from the countryside to the city in the winter.

From the point of view of food security, farms with a land area of less than 0.5 ha and residents of mountainous regions are among particularly high-risk groups. In Georgia, 98% is family farming. The consumption of home-cooked food is very high in villages - 53%, in small towns - 25%, in the mountains on average - 51%, and in bars - 31%. (Shatberashvili E, 2014). The segmentation of lands and small land ownership creates social causes in the development of poverty and food security.

¹ In the article, we present climate and environmental impact in one context, although the latter is a broader concept. (Regarding this, see: Overview of Environmental Risk Analysis by Financial Institutions, Network for Greening the

Financial System (NGFS), September, 202, p. 4.), https://www.ngfs.net/sites/default/files/medias/documents/overview_of_environmental_risk_analysis_by_financial_institutions.pdf

According to the 6th Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), climate adaptation in developing countries tends to be autonomous and focused on water-related management, while in developed countries, in contrast, it is focused more on urban-oriented policies (IPCC, 2022, 556).

Agriculture has the potential to reduce carbon dioxide emissions by improving cropland and pasture management, rehabilitating degraded soils, and better bioenergy and water management, in livestock - through rotational grazing systems, introducing organic manure management, methane capture (by the development of biogas production), improving feed and feed additives, and other.

Therefore, reforming agricultural policy and clarifying the direction in order to fight against environmental changes becomes a subject of discussion worldwide.

EU policy in the field of agriculture and climate change (CAP) consists of three directions - market promotion, income promotion, and rural development. With this aim, funds are allocated for direct subsidies of market-related expenses and for rural development. It also advocates "green subsidies" for the implementation of environmental/climate standards, subsidies for the development of young farming businesses, and grants (investment assistance, subsidies) for the development of degraded/contaminated regions.

In order to develop the agricultural sector in Georgia and mitigate the effects of climate change and reduce emissions, activities will be conducted in three directions: technological, economic-institutional, and social.

Rapid response to droughts, floods, and other extreme events in agriculture from a technological point of view requires the preparation and implementation of plans, the introduction of innovative methods of irrigation management and water use, as well as the reduction of the use of nitrogen-containing fertilizers, the prevention of the burning of agricultural waste; prevention of erosion, etc.

From an economic point of view, emphasis is placed on subsidies, insurance, and green financing through the introduction of various programs.

The importance and volume of green loans in the global world are increasing more and more (Green Credit Guarantee Schemes for MSMEs, 2022: Farah Imran Hussain, 2020). Its use in Georgia is only in an embryonic state, however, the focus in the future should be on the promotion of "green financing" policy, where the degree of state involvement (participation in loans, subsidies, insurance, and allocation of grants, etc.) will significantly increase the environmental impact policies. In this direction, the National Bank of Georgia has developed the concept of loan repayment in accordance with changes in climatic conditions (environment), as well as with social and governance issues, (ESG), the implementation of which began in 2022.

In the direction of agro-insurance, the main goal is to develop the insurance market in the agro-sector, promote agricultural activities, and increase the competitiveness of persons employed in the agricultural sector.

On the initiative of the Ministry of Environmental Protection and Agriculture of Georgia and with the financing of the Danish International Development Agency (DANIDA), the program for supporting young entrepreneurs in rural areas - "Young Entrepreneur" - was launched in 2018. The main task of the program is to promote economic growth and reduce poverty in the regions by providing financial and technical assistance to young people, and the main goal is to develop the private sector in the regions, promote the involvement of young people in business and make investments in the production/sale chain of agricultural products.

Institutional measures, in our view, will have a positive impact on the non-productive use of resources including the introduction of certification systems and the imposition of fees for ecological/environmental protection or climate services.

From the social point of view, the impact on the environment should be determined by the progress that the regions achieve with using of multi-factorial social indicators revealing food security, health status growth, education expansion in environmental issues, social awareness raising, and other.

All these measures are not exhaustive, the field is wide and there are many practical examples in the world to influence the environment, but their effectiveness is only fragmentary. Accordingly, there is a need for the generalization of complex, best practices, which should be preceded by the formation of a unified system of country assessments that will combine economic, management, and security rational activities.

References

1. Agriculture and Rural Development Strategy of Georgia 2021 – 2027, www.mepa.gov.ge December 2019, <https://mepa.gov.ge/Ge/Files/ViewFile/27243>
2. Green Credit Guarantee Schemes for MSMEs, 2022 (June), Alliance for Financial Inclusion, https://www.afi-global.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/06/Green-credit-schemes-for-MSMEs_260722.pdf
3. Farah Imran Hussain, Green loans: Financing the transition to a low-carbon economy APRIL 27, 2020, <https://blogs.worldbank.org/climatechange/green-loans-financing-transition-low-carbon-economy>
4. IPCC, 2022: Climate Change 2022: Impacts, Adaptation and Vulnerability. Contribution of Working Group II to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change [H.-O. Pörtner, D.C. Roberts, M. Tignor, E.S. Poloczanska, K. Mintenbeck, A. Alegría, M. Craig, S. Langsdorf, S. Löschke, V. Möller, A. Okem, B. Rama (eds.)]. Cambridge University Press. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK and New York, NY, USA, doi:10.1017/9781009325844 https://report.ipcc.ch/ar6/wg2/IPCC_AR6_WGII_FullReport.pdf
5. Ministry of Environment Protection and Agriculture of Georgia, Annual Report 2020, <https://mepa.gov>

6. Pavliashvili S., Gubeladze D. (2020), Agriculture, Economic Performance Management and the Circular Economy, Tb. (in Georgian)

7. Overview of Environmental Risk Analysis by Financial Institutions, Network for Greening the Financial System (NGFS), September, 202; https://www.ngfs.net/sites/default/files/medias/documents/overview_of_environmental_risk_analysis_by_financial_institutions.pdf

8. Shatberashvili E., Climate change and agriculture - mutual influence, current situation and ways to mitigate the impact, "Elkana" association, program: Institutionalization of climate change adaptation and impact mitigation measures in the regions of Georgia, Kachreti, April 12-14, 2014, (in Georgian), http://nala.ge/climatechange/uploads/TrainingModules/6_1.pdf